

"Study on Thioredoxin Systems: How to enhance photosynthesis in crop plants under fluctuating light?"

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Abstract

As global population continues to increase, demand for food and other plant-derived goods is on the rise. Enhancing photosynthesis could help meet this growing demand. Adaptation of photosynthetic machinery to fluctuating lights occurs at the expense of productivity causing significant losses. Chloroplastic thioredoxin systems are involved in balancing chloroplast metabolism to light availability by modulation of the activity of target proteins via reductive cleavage of disulfide linkages. Over-expression of NTRC, a thioredoxin system encoded in one peptide, in *Arabidopsis thaliana* results in improved CO₂ assimilation up to 20% in saturating and limiting light intensities and reduced non-photochemical quenching. Over-expression of TRXf, the main Calvin Cycle activator, in tobacco plants results in increased starch accumulation, though, unchanged CO₂ assimilation.

Introduction

Improving photosynthesis provides a promising alternative to meet the increased world demand for plant-derived goods. Research in the past 50 years has resulted in significant progress in our knowledge on plant molecular physiology (Foyer et al., 2017), which has led to discovery of new possible targets for enhancing photosynthesis. For instance, according to Long & Taylor (2017), transition from shade to light causes a significant 21% loss in productivity in wheat. This review focuses on strategies to improve photosynthesis in that aspect, under fluctuating light intensities, via an analysis on chloroplastic metabolism's redox regulation.

During daytime, crop plantations are exposed to constantly changing sunlight intensity that requires high level of stabilization (Foyer et al., 2017). Photosynthesis is a very dynamic and highly flexible process with many regulatory mechanisms that ensure optimal balancing under fluctuating light. For instance, at very high sunlight intensity crops absorb excess energy, which causes the activation of non-photochemical quenching (NPQ), a mechanism that dissipates excess energy to prevent damage. In addition, when environmental factor (e.g. clouds) or plants' structures cause intermittent shadowing of leaves,

plants need to adjust to light-dark and dark-light transitions. Shadowing of photosynthetic tissues leads to impaired energy-harvesting phase, thus inducing inactivation of energy-consuming machinery. Upon dark-light transition, plants must re-activate energy-consuming machinery and protective antioxidative mechanism because energy-harvesting activity tends to produce harmful byproducts e.g. reactive oxygen species (ROS).

Photosystem I (PSI) is a large protein complex of the chloroplastic electron transport chain involved in translating sunlight intensity into biochemical signals that can be passed onto proteins. PSI is equipped with pigments, such as chlorophyll, that absorb light energy, which is used to produce photo-excited electrons. Thioredoxins (TRXs) accept these electrons, hence becoming reduced, in a reaction catalyzed by thioredoxin-reductase (TRs) as displayed in figure 1. Reduced TRXs convey the message to target proteins by reducing target proteins' disulfide linkages to dithiol. This post-transcriptional modification triggers a structural change that alters the activity of target proteins (Nikkanen & Rintamäki, 2014). Usually, the modification induces activation, however, there are some examples of target proteins that become deactivated, for instance, STN7 kinase (Nikkanen & Rintamäki, 2014). Thus, plants transduce sunlight intensity to protein activity via disulfide linkage modifications using TRXs. This mechanism serves as a modulator of chloroplastic pathways. Some thioredoxin-regulated pathways include Calvin-Cycle (Nikkanen & Rintamäki, 2014), ATP-synthesis (Hisabori et al., 2013), non-photochemical quenching (Naranjo et al., 2016) and antioxidative defense (Nikkanen et al., 2017).

Thioredoxin proteins

TRXs are a family of small ubiquitous oxidoreductase involved in redox-regulation and signaling. They have a redox active dithiol/disulfide motif in their active site. When this motif is in its reduced form, it used to induce reductive cleavage of disulfide linkages in target proteins via bimolecular nucleophilic attack (Nikkanen & Rintamäki, 2014). Oxidized TRXs are reactivated/reduced by TRs. The combination of TRX-TR is referred to as thioredoxin system. There are two TRs in chloroplasts: ferredoxin-dependent TR (FTR) and NADPH-dependent TR (NTR). The former obtains electrons from ferredoxin, previously photo-reduced by PSI, while the latter relies on NADPH for electron supply (figure 1).

Plant expression of TRXs is not limited to photosynthetic tissues. However, a large fraction of TRXs are expressed in photosynthetic tissue, of which many are localized to chloroplasts which emphasizes the importance of redox regulation in chloroplast metabolism (Nikkanen et al., 2017). The group of chloroplast-localized TRXs includes classical TRXs, NTRC (NADPH thioredoxin reductase C), ACHT (Atypical Cys His-rich TRXs) and TRX-like proteins (Nikkanen et al.,

2017). Classical TRXs, characterized by a conserved redox active motif “WCGPC” (Balsera et al., 2013), are subdivided into *f*, *m*, *x*, *y* and *z* types. In *A. thaliana*, the model organism for plant science, TRX*f*, TRX*m* and TRX*y* have two, four and two isoforms respectively (Buchanan & Balmer, 2005). All the classical TRXs have been shown experimentally to be reduced by FTR, except for TRX*z*, whose inability to interact with FTR could be attributed to its surface (Toivola et al., 2013).

The protein NTRC, identified by Serrato et al. (2004), is rather remarkable because it combines in a single peptide a complete thioredoxin system: a TRX-domain at the C-terminus and an NADPH-dependent TR-domain at the N-terminus. In the chloroplast, NTRC is found as a homodimer where the TR-domain of a subunit reduces the other subunit’s TRX-domain (Pérez-Ruiz & Cejudo, 2009). Moreover, NTRC can be active in dark conditions because the oxidative pentose pathway (OPP) supplies NADPH in a light-independent manner. NTRC and classic TRXs-FTR are the two-main photosynthetic regulatory thioredoxin systems. Initially believed to work independently, Nikkanen et al. (2016) and Thormählen et al. (2015) obtained strong evidence for collaboration between these two systems via the study of transgenic *A. thaliana* lines.

Table 1. Targets of TRX*f* and NTRC with their respective experimental evidence.

Thioredoxin	Target	Function	Evidence
TRX <i>f</i>	FBPase	Calvin Cycle	<i>in planta</i> - Nikkanen et al. (2016)
	SBPase	Calvin Cycle	<i>in vitro</i> - Nishizawa & Buchanan. (1981)
	B-GADPH	Calvin Cycle	<i>in vitro</i> - Marri et al. (2009)
	PRK	Calvin Cycle	<i>in planta</i> - Nikkanen et al. (2016) and <i>in vitro</i> - Marri et al. (2009)
	CP12	Calvin Cycle regulation	<i>in vitro</i> - Marri et al. (2009)
	αRCA	Rubisco regulation	<i>in vitro</i> - Zhang et al. (1999)
	AGPase	Starch synthesis	<i>in vitro</i> - Geigenberger et al. (2005)
	ATP synthase	ATP synthesis	<i>in vitro</i> - McKinney et al. (1978)
NTRC	FBPase	Calvin Cycle	<i>in planta</i> - Nikkanen et al. (2016)
	PRK	Calvin Cycle	<i>in planta</i> - Nikkanen et al. (2016)
	AGPase	Starch synthesis	<i>in vitro</i> - Michalska et al. (2009)
	2-Cys-PRXs	Peroxide detoxification	<i>in vivo</i> - Bernal-Bayard et al. (2014)
	ATP synthase	ATP synthesis	<i>ntrc</i> knock-out mutant - Carrillo et al. (2016)

Figure 1. Interactome of TRXf and NTRC displaying their main targets. This figure is a representation of the interactions of TRXf and NTRC that are relevant to the subject of enhancing photosynthesis. The omission of some chloroplast electron transport chain proteins and thioredoxin targets is for clarity sake. Calvin Cycle enzymes are labelled in dark green. Dark grey arrows represent the movement of electrons, while black arrow represents the synthesis of NADPH from the oxidative pentose pathway (OPP).

Key Enzymes: PSI (Photosystem I), Fd (Ferredoxin), FTR (Ferredoxin-dependent Thioredoxin Reductase), FNR (Ferredoxin-NADP⁺ Reductase), NTRC (NADPH thioredoxin reductase C), 2-Cys-PRXs (2-cysteine-peroxiredoxins), AGPase (ADP-glucosyl pyrophosphorylase), PRK (Phosphoribulokinase), FBPase (Fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase), SBPase (Sedoheptulose-1,7-bisphosphatase), CP12 (Calvin Cycle protein CP12), GADPH (NADP-glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GADPH) and RCA (Rubisco Activase). Other abbreviations: OPP (Oxidative Pentose Pathway), NADPH (Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate), TRd (Thioredoxin Reductase Domain) and TRXd (Thioredoxin Domain).

Thioredoxin's targets

Calvin-Benson-Bassham Cycle

The Calvin-Benson-Bassham Cycle is divided in three steps: fixation, reduction and regeneration. The process involves the products of light-driven reactions (NADPH and ATP) and 11 enzymes, which catalyze 13 reactions (figure 2). After elucidation of the cycle, enzymes of the cycle were purified and studied in detail. This helped discover four enzymes (FBPase, SBPase, GADPH and PRK, figure 1) that displayed a light-dependent redox-regulated activity. These enzymes have

pairs of regulatory cysteine residues oxidized and inactive in the dark and; reduced and active in the light. These findings explained that the Calvin Cycle becomes active in the sunlight, and inactive in the dark via redox-regulation of its enzymes. However, Michelet et al. (2013) shows how recent proteomic studies suggest that not only these four enzymes (and Rubisco Activase) of the Calvin Cycle are redox-regulated, but the eleven enzymes are involved in redox-regulation via various post-translational modifications, for instance nitrosylation.

Fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase (FBPase). It catalyzes the dephosphorylation of fructose-1,6-bisphosphate to produce fructose-6-phosphate and inorganic phosphate using Mg^{2+} cofactor. The reaction is part of the regeneration step. The enzyme is found as a homotetramer and it forms a heterodimer with TRX upon light-dependent activation, which is strictly dependent to both isoforms of TRXf (Dai et al., 2004). In the oxidized conformation, the active site only reaches 20-30% activity due to a dysfunctional conformation, which does not accommodate efficiently Mg^{2+} . (Michelet et al., 2013). The conformational changes induced by TRX-mediated reduction result in a catalytically optimal conformation. To further emphasize FBPase fine-tuning to light, FBPase optimal pH is slightly above normal stromal pH which is only achieved with light-driven proton pumping to thylakoid lumen.

NADP-glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GADPH). It catalyzes the reduction of 1,3-bisphosphoglycerate to produce glyceraldehyde-3 phosphate using preferably NADPH, could also use NAD cofactor (Fermani et al., 2007). Similar to FBPase, its activity is optimal in mildly alkaline conditions (Trost et al., 2006). GAPDH is found as a tetramer composed of the two forms, A and B, A_2B_2 or solely of A-form (A_4). A-form lacks regulatory cysteine residues making it insensitive to TRX-mediated regulation. However, A_4 is regulated by S-glutathionylation of catalytic cysteine residue (Fermani et al., 2007) and CP12-mediated aggregation with phosphoribulokinase (PRK). B-form is believed to be the product of gene duplication of A-form plus fusion with C-terminus of CP12 (Petersen et al., 2006). The C-terminus fused domain has a pair of cysteine residues that confers TRX-mediated regulation. Oxidized B-form induces oligomerization of A_2B_2 into inactive hexadecamer A_8B_8 (Gontero & Salvucci, 2014) and reduces NADPH-activity, effectively down-regulating A_2B_2 (Trost et al., 2006).

Sedoheptulose-1,7-bisphosphatase (SBPase). It catalyzes the dephosphorylation of sedoheptulose-1,7-bisphosphate to produce sedoheptulose-7-bisphosphate and inorganic phosphate. Similar to FBPase, SBPase uses Mg^{2+} cofactor and the reaction catalyzed is part of the regeneration phase. This reaction determines whether assimilated carbon is used in the regenerative phase or diverted to synthesize other organic compounds e.g. sucrose (Ding et al., 2016). The enzyme, unique to photosynthetic organisms, is found as a homodimer. In the dark, oxidized SBPase is completely inactive. The molecular

mechanism for activation by reduction of disulfide bridge remains unclear, perhaps through general conformational change of the active site (Michelet et al., 2013). Experimental evidence indicates TRXf-mediated activation (Nishizawa & Buchanan, 1981). SBPase activity is also pH-dependent: at acidic stromal pH (dark conditions), SBPase is inactive (Ding et al., 2016). Under saturating light and CO₂ conditions, Calvin Cycle is partially controlled by SBPase activity (Gontero & Salvucci, 2014). Therefore, SBPase is a potential target to enhance photosynthesis. This is corroborated by data from Ding et al. (2016), where increased SBPase activity leads to increased photosynthetic capacity. Given the constant increase in CO₂ levels due to global warming, this data could potentially be of high importance.

Phosphoribulokinase (PRK). It catalyzes the phosphorylation of ribulose-5-phosphate to ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate (RuBP) using ATP generated by light-driven reactions. The reaction is part of the regenerative step. Found exclusively in the chloroplasts, PRK is a homodimer. Oxidized PRK has a low basal activity and it is activated most efficiently by TRXf (Michelet et al., 2013). The pair of regulatory cysteine residues when in disulfide conformation, block the enzymatic activity. The mechanism involves the inability of a regulatory cysteine to bind ribulose-5-phosphate, unless in reduced state (Michelet et al., 2013). In addition, PRK and GAPDH have another form of redox-regulation involving CP12, an intrinsically disordered protein regulated by TRXf and *m*, in vitro evidence from López-Calcano (2014). Oxidized CP12 forms rapidly a complex with GAPDH and PRK, regardless of their redox state, decreasing their activity. Upon CP12 reduction, complex is dissociated. These changes respond to light intensity: high light leads to dissociation within 1 minute and transfer to low light caused association within 1 minute (López-Calcano et al., 2014). Therefore, CP12-regulation of Calvin Cycle enzymes provides a rapid response to fluctuating light.

RubisCo Activase (RCA): RuBisCo catalyzes the first reaction of the Calvin Cycle, the CO₂ fixation to RuBP to produce two molecules of 3-phosphoglyceric acid. This tends to be the rate-limiting step in photosynthesis (Sidhu et al., 2014) due to RuBisCo inefficient enzymatic activity and long activation time. Hence, RuBisCo has been widely studied as a possible target to enhance photosynthesis. Given its metabolic importance, RubisCo is highly regulated. It is only active when the ε-amine of a catalytic lysine residue is carbamylated (Gontero & Salvucci, 2014). Moreover, a range of substrates, including RuBP, stabilize the inactive conformation of RubisCo (Carmo-Silva & Salvucci, 2013). RCA is an AAA+ ATPase with a chaperone activity that uses ATP-hydrolysis to release tightly bound substrates from RubisCo active sites, thus remodeling RubisCo to render it catalytically competent (Gontero & Salvucci, 2014). Due to RCA's need for ATP and its inhibition by ADP, it adjusts the rate of CO₂ assimilation to the light-driven reactions via modulating RuBisCo activation state (Carmo-Silva & Salvucci, 2013). RCA's ADP-inhibition is modulated by TRX-

regulation only in plants expressing α RCA. The α -isoform is redox-sensitive as it has a ~ 25 amino acid extension, when compared to β -isoform, with a pair of regulatory cysteine residues regulated by TRXf (Zhang & Portis, 1999). However, not all crop plants encode α -isoform, e.g. corn, and still retain RuBisCo activity modulated to light irradiance demonstrating heterogeneity in RCA regulation (Carmo-Silva & Salvucci, 2013). *A. thaliana* expresses both isoforms. The regulation mechanism is based on a reduced sensitivity for ADP-inhibition in reduced α -isoform, then the redox-state of α -isoform is conferred to the RCA holoenzyme (Carmo-Silva & Salvucci, 2013).

Figure 2. Scheme illustrating the steps for the Calvin Cycle with the respective enzymes. The enzymes labelled with a yellow star are thioredoxin-regulated. RubisCo has two stars since it is indirectly thioredoxin-regulated by α -Rubisco Activase. The green arrows of the reaction catalyzed by transketolase represent the same reaction: $GAP + F6P \rightarrow Xu5P + E4P$.) Each time the cycle is run, one molecule of GAP goes into Carbohydrate synthesis.

Key Molecules: RuBP (ribulose biphosphate), 3PG (3-phosphoglyceric acid), BPG (2,3-biphosphoglyceric acid), GAP (glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate), E4P (erythrose 4-phosphate), DHAP (Dihydroxyacetone phosphate), FBP (fructose-1,6-biphosphate), F6P (fructose-6-phosphate), Xu5P (xylulose-5-phosphate), Ru5P (ribulose-5-phosphate), SBP (seduheptulose-1,7-biphosphate), S7P (seduheptulose-7-phosphate) and R5P (ribose-5-phosphate).

ATP synthesis

The proton motive force (pmf) consists of the build-up of electrochemical gradient across the thylakoid membrane, which is caused by pumping protons into the thylakoid lumen by light-driven photosynthetic proteins. ATP-synthase is a ubiquitous essential enzyme involved in ATP-synthesis. Chloroplast ATP-synthase, structurally and functionally is highly similar to mitochondrial ATP-synthase. Chloroplast ATP-synthase utilizes the pmf across the thylakoid membrane to drive the phosphorylation of ADP to produce ATP. The structure and mechanism of action of this enzyme is explained in detail in Wolfgang & Nelson (2015). The γ -subunit of F_1 catalytic core displays redox-regulation with Cys199 and Cys205 in *A. thaliana* (Carrillo et al., 2016), that allows synchronization between light irradiance and ATP-synthase activity. ATP-synthase activity requires a threshold pmf which is decreased with reduced γ -subunit (Kohzuma et al., 2017). Therefore, reduced ATP-synthase shows higher activity at low light. Carrillo et al. (2016) used *ntrc* knock-out line of *A. thaliana* to elaborate a dual-mode redox-regulation mechanism. In low light, NTRC is the primary reductant, as indicated by strong acidification of thylakoid lumen due to impaired ATP-synthase activation in *ntrc*. While in high light, ATP-synthase becomes fully reduced in this line, indicating that TRXf mediates this reduction. This is in agreement with Kohzuma et al. (2017), Nikkanen et al. (2016) and Naranjo et al. (2016) papers. The dual-mode mechanism ensures rapid activation of ATP-synthase, even at low lights, in order to prevent harmful acidification of the thylakoid lumen.

Even though ATP-synthase does not limit photosynthesis per se, impaired activation of ATP-synthase triggers induction of NPQ. In turn, NPQ relaxation temporarily limits photosynthesis, as it is considerably slower than induction (Kromdijk et al., 2016). *ntrc* knock-out lines of *A. thaliana*, which have impaired activation of ATP-synthase at low light have high levels of NPQ (Naranjo et al., 2016). The mechanism relies on qE, the major component of NPQ in plant leaves (Naranjo et al., 2016). qE requires zeaxanthin, acidified thylakoid lumen and PsbS protein from PSII. Production and turnover of zeaxanthin are catalyzed by violaxanthin de-epoxidase (VDE) and zeaxanthin epoxidase (ZE) respectively. Both enzymes appeared to be potentially redox-regulated: VDE becomes deactivated upon reduction via treatment with dithiothreitol (DTT) *in vitro* (Simionato et al., 2015), while ZE inactive aggregates are dissociated upon NTRC reduction *in vitro* (Naranjo et al., 2016). These regulations could account partially for high NPQ in *ntrc* mutants, decreased deactivation of VDE and decreased activation of ZE. However, *ntrc* lines showed the same redox state in both enzymes compared to WT. Therefore, increased NPQ is caused by acidification of the thylakoid lumen due to impaired ATP-synthase activation. Thylakoid lumen acidification causes qE induction via decreased pH and

increased zeaxanthin levels as VDE activity is pH-dependent (Naranjo et al., 2016).

Oxidation Loop

Thioredoxin-mediated activation of target proteins is transient and reversible. Knowledge on the reversible reaction, i.e. oxidation of target proteins, is limited. In theory, accumulation of oxidants results in target protein oxidation. Schürmann (1983) provides evidence indicating the transfer of electrons from thioredoxin-reduced cysteine residues in target proteins to molecular oxygen directly or via oxidized TRXs. Schürmann & Buchanan (2008) provide evidence by showing a four-fold increase in FBPase deactivation in the presence of molecular oxygen, in comparison to anaerobic conditions (Schürmann & Buchanan, 2008). Deactivation via oxidized TRXs relies on the reversibility of activation/reduction. Similar redox potentials of TRXs and target proteins allows reversibility of the reaction (Nikkanen & Rintamäki, 2014). Alterations of the chemical environment, such as pH changes or ligand binding to target proteins, could shift the midpoint redox potential of thioredoxin-regulated enzymes favouring oxidation, hence deactivation (Schürmann & Buchanan, 2008).

Another possible mechanism for target protein deactivation involves 2-Cys-PRXs (2-Cysteine-peroxiredoxin). 2-Cys-PRXs are a group of enzymes that catalyze H₂O₂ detoxification via oxidation of their two catalytic cysteine residues (Pulido et al., 2010). Dangoor et al. (2012) demonstrated that accumulation of oxidized 2-Cys-PRXs drives the deactivation/oxidation of ACHT1 (Dangoor et al., 2012). Then, regeneration of reduced 2-Cys-PRXs is catalysed predominantly by NTRC, and by TRX_x (Pulido et al., 2010). Therefore, as Nikkanen et al. (2017) suggest, 2-Cys-PRXs might be part of an oxidizing loop for chloroplastic redox-regulated enzymes and thioredoxins. Further evidence is provided by Nikkanen et al. (2017), as high accumulation of oxidized 2-Cys-PRXs in *ntrc* knock-out lines of *A. thaliana* correlates with oxidation of redox-regulated Calvin cycle enzymes (Nikkanen et al., 2016).

Therefore, TRX-mediated activation is transient; hence, a continuous supply of reduced TRXs is required in order to keep enzymes active. This feature allows fine-tuning of chloroplastic pathways to varying light intensities (Nikkanen & Rintamäki, 2014).

Strategies to improve photosynthesis

Overexpression of NTRC

Nikkanen et al. (2016) created a transgenic line of *A. thaliana* over-expressing NTRC (OE-NTRC). This line showed enhanced photosynthesis in terms of increased CO₂ assimilation and reduced NPQ which resulted in increased dry weight and leaf size. CO₂ assimilation increased by 20% when light limited or saturated photosynthesis i.e. low light and high light intensities.

The increase in CO₂ assimilation in OE-NTRC is highly probable to be the result of improvements in numerous NTRC-dependent pathways, the overall scheme is displayed in figure 3. For instance, improved activation of Calvin Cycle enzymes, especially at low light intensity. This improvement is evident by the fractions of reduced PRK and FBPase which was greater in OE-NTRC at low, normal and high light intensities; 50, 500 and 1000 μmol of photons $\text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ respectively. This is in accordance with the increased levels of reduced TRXf (97% in OE-NTRC compared to 17% in WT upon illumination), since TRXf is known to reduce both enzymes. Even in the dark, when most TRXf is oxidized, OE-NTRC showed 30% TRXf reduced. Theoretically, other Calvin Cycle enzymes (e.g. SBPase) would also benefit from increased activation rates and greater fraction of reduced form. Enhanced photosynthesis under saturating light could to some extent be due to improved activation of SBPase, which would be in agreement with Ding et al. (2016). Unfortunately, no data on SBPase redox-state was recorded.

In addition, PSI acceptor side limitation decreased in OE-NTRC. The excess of NTRC may prevent over-reduction of PSI due to greater amount of targets for reduced Fd, mostly Fd-NADP⁺ reductase (FNR) to regenerate NADPH (Figure 1). Over-reduction of PSI could potentially damage PSI complex as shown by an extremely high acceptor side limitation in *trxf1-ntrc* double knock-out (Thormahlen et al., 2015).

OE-NTRC showed reduced NPQ which is also associated with a better use of light energy and thus, enhanced photosynthesis. The γ -subunit of ATP-synthase is reduced even in the dark in OE-NTRC, effectively preventing acidification of the thylakoid lumen. Consequently, combination of low zeaxanthin levels and more neutral pH leads to decreased qE induction, hence decreased NPQ. Constitutively reduced ATP-synthase provide the means to decrease NPQ, possibly at the expense of futile ATP-hydrolysis.

Furthermore, OE-NTRC augments the reduced stromal state. This is appreciable by observing the redox state of 2-Cys-PRXs. 2-Cys-PRXs tends to be mostly reduced in the light in WT. Surprisingly, even in dark-adapted leaves, OE-NTRC had some 2-Cys-PRXs. These high levels of reduced 2-Cys-PRXs have two major advantages: (1) they supply the plant with a more active H₂O₂-detoxifying mechanism and (2) they alter the proposed oxidizing loop allowing thioredoxin-

regulated enzymes to be reduced for longer periods of time. The first advantage would be more evident under low light as 2-Cys-PRXs uses other reducing agents at high light intensities (Naranjo et al., 2016).

Chloroplast redox-regulation is a system of high inter-connectivity and dynamicity. Modifying components of the system, such over-expression of NTRC, alters the balance. This alteration of the balance causes a variety of consequences that could be beneficial or detrimental. The phenotype of OE-NTRC plants demonstrates very clearly that beneficial consequences outweigh the detrimental. Among the detrimental consequences, there is special emphasis on a 20% decrease in seed production in OE-NTRC since a large group of crop plants are harvested for their seeds (e.g. wheat or corn) (Nikkanen, unpublished).

Figure 3. Interactome of TRXf and NTRC in OE-NTRC transgenic *A. thaliana* lines. Figure adapted from Nikkanen et al. (2016). The red arrows represent the hypothetical increase in these reactions given the excess NTRC. The key enzymes and other abbreviations are identical to

Overexpression of TRXf

Sanz-Barrio et al. (2013) created transgenic lines over-expressing TRXf (OE-TRXf) in tobacco plants. *G10Lf* line resulted in 20-fold and *psbAf* in 200-fold increase in TRXf levels compared to WT. These lines showed maximal increase in starch and sucrose content at the end of their growth cycle. Surprisingly, *G10Lf* showed greater starch accumulation than *psbAf*. Probably, this is due to TRXf

ability to form homo-oligomers (Sanz-Barrio et al., 2012), so excess TRXf form non-functional oligomers. The specific leaf weight increased by 20% in *G10Lf*, possibly as a result of increased accumulation of carbohydrates. Unfortunately, steady-state photosynthesis did not improve. CO₂ assimilation rates, plant growth and leaf size remained similar to WT.

The exact way OE-TRXf led to augmented starch accumulation remains unknown. Measurements of starch content over day-night periods demonstrated no change in pattern of starch synthesis or starch degradation compared to WT. Unchanged starch synthesis is corroborated by no apparent change in activation of AGPase (ADP-glucose pyrophosphorylase), a crucial redox-regulated enzyme that catalyzes the first committed step in starch synthesis, in OE-TRXf. AGPase activation state is unresponsive to excess TRXf. However, *trxf1* knock-out in *A. thaliana* leads to delayed light-dependent activation of AGPase (Thormahlen et al., 2013). Moreover, once activated, AGPase only reaches 50% activity compared to WT. Therefore, AGPase might be operating at its maximal already in WT or could be limited by allosteric regulators or inhibitors in OE-TRXf (Sanz-Barrio et al., 2013). In addition, the weak relation between AGPase redox regulation and starch accumulation is further demonstrated in experiments using redox-insensitive AGPase where starch accumulation either remains unchanged (Li et al., 2012) or slightly increased (Hädrich et al., 2012).

The overall findings of this paper are of significant importance to biofuel production. Although photosynthesis rate did not improve, there was a four-fold increase in ethanol derived from *G10Lf* plants. Therefore, OE-TRXf tobacco plants have great potential of becoming nonfood energy crop for biofuel production.

Conclusion

This dissertation reviewed up-to-date literature on thioredoxin systems and investigated the experimental evidence for their modification with the purpose of enhancing photosynthesis. The most promising discovery discussed in this paper is the improvement in CO₂ assimilation by 20% in OE-NTRC *A. thaliana* lines. The potential of OE-TRXf tobacco plants has also been proposed for biofuel production given the hyperaccumulation of starch and four-fold increase in ethanol derived from OE-TRXf tobacco plants.

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